

Evaluation of Group Medicare Annual Wellness Visits Using PPM

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Background

- **Affordable Care Act (ACA) became law (2011)**
Provision: Annual Wellness Visit (AWV) with Personal Preventive Services (PPS)
- **Medicare stopped payment for Physical Exams**
 - Recipients entitled to AWV w/PPS without cost sharing every 12 months
 - Eligible providers: MD, DO, NP, PA
- Motivational Interviewing (MI) used to elicit essential behavior changes in maintaining health/preventing chronic disease among elderly patients

Problem

- Anticipated access problems at local hospital with ACA (↑ 33,000 new members)
- Limited time to counsel older adults on common health issues
- Efficiency: 40 minutes of individual visits with MD and 20 minutes with LVN/MA

Aims

- Process evaluation of the actual implementation of a nurse practitioner-run Group Medicare AWV utilizing PRECEDE-PROCEED MODEL (PPM) as a guide.
- Evaluate and compare quality indicators (depression, fall risk, and memory loss): Group AWVs vs. individual AWVs.

Methods

Target Population

- Senior Kaiser Permanente (KP) Health Plan members at KP Medical Center in Panorama City covered by Medicare Part B
- Most with one or more chronic conditions

Setting

Ambulatory care clinic (moderately diverse patients, ↑Latinos, Filipinos) in San Fernando Valley CA

Theoretical Framework: PRECEDE-PROCEED MODEL

Planning Phase: Predisposing, Reinforcing, Enabling, Constructs in Educational Diagnosis and Evaluation
Evaluation Phase: Policy, Regulatory, Organizational Constructs in Educational and Environmental Development

Group Medicare Annual Wellness Visit (GAWV)

GAWV - collaborative appointment with the NP, health educator, and a nurse extender (LVN/MA). Alternative means of providing AWV with PPS (vs. individual AWV). Averages 90 -120 minutes with 6 - 18 patients. NP sees patients individually during appointment. Handouts used to expedite visits. Patients advised to ask questions, discuss issues with primary care providers.

AWV requirements:

- (1) Acquire beneficiary information (VS, health history questionnaire)
- (2) Begin assessment including health risks (Review health record, health history, care management summary sheet)
- (3) Counsel beneficiary (Discuss results of lab tests and procedures, action planning with goal setting).

Motivational Interviewing (MI)

- Integrating motivational interviewing (MI) in GAWV leads to behavior changes and improved self-management:
 - MI outperforms advice giving
 - MI helpful across a range of diseases
- NP and health educator trained in MI techniques

Results

- Steps of PRECEDE-PROCEED model followed, with exception of lack of initial patient input and involvement; this allowed several preventable problems to occur.
- Trial and error for patient recruitment.
- 2013-2016
 - GAWV attendance ↑ 6% to 26% of total AWVs.
 - ↑ test completion rates on 3 QI indicators in patients seen in GAWV vs. individual AWV.
 - KP Panorama City ↑ completion rates vs. 12 SoCal medical centers, due to GAWVs.
 - GAWV patients deemed high risk on indicators referred to specialists (not done consistently with individual AWVs).
- ↑ patient satisfaction:
 - 100% patients glad they participated
 - 99% would recommend GAWV to family/friend.
- Group visit cost:
 - \$51/patient in group of 6
 - \$38/patient in group of 12
 - \$85/patient seen 1:1
- Estimated savings from preventing fall injury among 30% of 60 high risk patients = \$600,000

Recommendations

1. Implement GAWVs throughout Southern CA Region.
2. Standardize AWVs referral practices for positive screens (depression, fall risk, and memory loss)
3. Allot dedicated time and resources to Group AWV providers to prevent GAWV abandonment
4. Integrate and use MI in GAWVs; provide education in MI to new GAWV providers